

An Examination of the Dynamic Predictive Validity Thesis

Thomas K. Arnold

University of Cincinnati

Abstract

One of the more enduring puzzles in criminology is the combination of both stability and change in criminal behavior over the life course. This study examines how the criminal offender's risk of recidivism changes over time and provides guidance for criminology, forensic psychology, and criminal justice. A multidisciplinary approach leads to improvements in the methods of dynamic risk assessment, and provides an analysis of the stability and dynamism present in offender risk levels, both between and within individuals. Methods are demonstrated for improving measurement accuracy in test-retest environments, and creating measurement criteria to determine the change in risk score needed to predict a change in recidivism. Results include comparisons of between group and within group changes in risk levels over time, indications of how the rank order levels of risk change over time, measurements of the temporal stability of risk, and an indication that changes in risk are typically nonlinear, rather than linear in nature. An analysis of the results is presented that suggests methods for improving the risk assessment process, precautions needed when measuring results from treatment programs, ways to improve desistance research, and future directions for theory.

An Examination of the Dynamic Predictive Validity Thesis

The “dynamic predictive validity thesis” is a thesis regarding the properties of offender risk assessment instruments that was developed over the space of about a decade by Andrews, Robinson, Bonta, and Motiuk (Andrews & Robinson, 1984). This thesis became a popular measure of the quality of offender risk assessment instruments and dynamic predictive validity was listed as a required attribute by several state level criminal justice organizations.

The present article will demonstrate that the dynamic predictive validity thesis, as it is currently being practiced, is both conceptually and methodologically flawed. Moreover, it will be demonstrated that dynamic predictive validity, as it is currently being measured, is probably an indicator of poor performance for an offender risk assessment instrument. It appears that an offender risk assessment with dynamic predictive validity may simply be too subjective and is in need of simplification to avoid subjectivity in rating. These two issues will be examined using evidence collected from offender reassessment scores and the principles of psychometric theory.

The logic model behind the dynamic predictive validity thesis is simple and appealing. The model proposes that criminal offender recidivism risk is “dynamic” and that the predictive validity of offender risk assessment instruments improves between two points in time because the second assessment measures the “newer” risk level more accurately than the “older” risk assessment.

This thesis is flawed on two levels. First, the concept of “dynamic” is flawed. The propensity for recidivism risk is much more dynamic than previously supposed. Second, tests of dynamic predictive validity are confounded by the potential for changes in two separate measures, a) actual recidivism risk, and b) perceived recidivism risk. An expanded examination

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

4

of the data suggests that dynamic predictive validity is a function of changes in perceived risk by raters rather than systematic improvement in risk accuracy through reassessment.

, if an offender's risk level is assessed at two points in time with an assessment instrument that measures risk factors which can change over time, and the risk score changes between assessments, it can be assumed that the offender's risk of committing a crime has changed. Unfortunately, such simple ideas seldom ever work as intended, and this appears to be the case in this situation. There are many things can cause a risk score to change that have nothing to do with a change in offender risk, and this article provides an analysis of just a few of those things.

, Offender risk classification is an important function in corrections. Knowledge of the level of offender risk can help improve community safety by indicating which criminal offenders are the most likely to commit new crimes. Modern risk assessment instruments typically use structured interviews and record searches to develop a risk score. If the risk assessment instrument is designed properly for the offender population, the magnitude of the risk score has a linear relationship with the level of recidivism in the period after the risk assessment.

One of the more recent advances in offender risk classification has been the development of "dynamic" risk assessment instruments (Bonta, 1996). Dynamic risk assessment instruments, such as the Level of Service Inventory-Revised (LSI-R; Andrews, & Bonta, 1995), include a number of risk factors that can change over time, such as employment history, financial status, housing, antisocial attitudes, etc. Because of these dynamic risk measures, it is believed that it will be possible to measure changes in offender risk that occur over time.

The assertion that changes in offender risk can be measured has been based upon a series of studies that have measured improvements in prediction accuracy when risk scores were

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

5

collected at two points in time that are six or more months apart (Andrews, & Robinson, 1984; Arnold, 2007; Motiuk, 1991, Motiuk, Bonta, & Andrews, 1990; Raynor, 2007, Raynor, Kynch, Roberts, & Merrington, 2000, Vose, 2008). In these studies, the second risk scores have been consistently better at predicting recidivism than the first scores when both scores are used as a predictor of recidivism in the time period after assessment two. The reason suggested for the improvement in prediction accuracy is that if offender risk changed between assessments, and one is measuring risk with a dynamic risk assessment instrument, the second score should be a more accurate measure than the first.

An alternative hypothesis is available however, and this was suggested in the first test to measure improvements in prediction accuracy (Andrews, & Robinson, 1984). They suggested that:

The major issue is whether the relative value of retest scores reflected actual change in the person and/or situation of probationers or simply more accurate assessments on the part of officers. For example, the relative superiority of reassessments may have reflected increased knowledge of the situations of probationers rather than real changes in their situations. (p. 5)

If this were the case, changes in score leading to improvements in prediction accuracy might have everything to do with changes in rater accuracy and nothing to do with changes in offender risk. Experiments to test this hypothesis do not appear to ever have been conducted. The primary hypothesis that offender risk changes in six months, and these changes in risk can be measured, has become the accepted belief and “best practice” in corrections (Andrews, & Bonta, 2006: p. 290; Andrews & Bonta, et. al., 1990:p. 32; Bonta, 2002:p. 368, Kreamer, 2004, Peters, & Wexler, 2005; p. 40).

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

6

Arnold (2007), using risk scores generated with the LSI-R, found evidence to support the alternative hypothesis of rater improvement while working on his master's thesis. The primary difference between the tests done by Arnold and those done in the previous studies was the inclusion of multiple waves of analysis. In addition to testing for improvements in prediction accuracy from assessment one to assessment two, tests were conducted to see if prediction improved from assessment two to assessment three, and from assessment three to assessment four. As in the other studies, prediction did improve between the first and second assessments, but in contrast to the results for the first wave, prediction did not improve between assessments two and three or between assessments three and four. This is exactly what one would expect if rating was improving from assessment one to two. If rating was improving due to a better understanding of the offender by the rater, there should be a "learning curve" where no further improvements would be seen after a certain amount of time. If this learning curve is causing the improvement in prediction, and no further improvements in prediction are seen after six months, this begs the question; can changes in offender risk be measured? This study provides a set of analyses that attempt to answer this question.

The Precision of Offender Risk Assessment Instruments

There does not appear to be an indication in the assessment literature that indicates the size of change in LSI score required in order for there to be a change in violation rate. To use the words of Bateson (1979: p. 99), the magnitudes of the "differences that make a difference" are not known. Problems with measurement accuracy have been encountered before in other disciplines such as psychology, where there are problems with interpretation of test-retest scores. Two possible problems are measurement errors and temporal instability in the item being

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

7

assessed (Jacobson, & Truax, 1991; Jacobson, et. al., 1984). Jacobson and others have developed a statistical formula that can be used to determine the amount of change that is needed to make a clinically significant difference in outcome, given the inaccuracies that are inherent in the measurement process. Clinically significant change, in terms of LSI scores, would indicate a change in score large enough to predict a significant change in violation rates.

One way to determine the level of clinically significant change is to use a Reliable Change Index (RCI). The RCI provides a cutoff score that indicates the level of change in assessment score needed to produce a change in the behavior of interest. The formula for the RCI at a 95% probability level, taken from Smith, & Beaton (2008: 289), is

$$RCI = 1.96 * \text{SQRT}(2) * S.D._1 * \text{SQRT}(1 - r_{1-2})$$

Where $S.D._1$ is the standard deviation of the measurement score on the first assessment, and r_{1-2} is the correlation between the first and second sets of assessment scores in a period of no change. The calculation of the RCI will be done in as part of this analysis, as well as a regression test using dummy variables to determine the level of score change that is required to assure that there has been a significant change in the actual risk of recidivism. This will provide a way to discern random changes in score from true temporal instability.

METHODS

Sample Demographics

The LSI records used in the present study were collected by probation officers in a Midwestern county community corrections department from 2002 to 2006. LSI assessments were done on 4919 separate offenders, 1833 with a second assessment, 962 with a third

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

8

assessment, etc., and 12 offenders with eight LSI assessments. The shrinking sample was of some concern, as Cook and Campbell (1979) had noted that selection bias might cause problems with the generalizability of results found in a biased sample. The samples were approximately 80% white and 80% male, with a mean age of about 34 years (S.D.=10), and a mean initial LSI score of approximately 25 (S.D.=8).

There were several known reasons for the shrinkage in the number of offenders with subsequent assessments. The records were collected over several years, and offenders who were assessed later in the collection cycle did not have as many reassessments. The county, adhering to the risk principle, generally only reassessed more serious offenders, leading to a lower number of low risk offenders. About half the low risk offenders who were assessed again had come back into the assessment stream because of a new violation. The other half were apparently given closer scrutiny for some other reason, perhaps because of violence or sexual offending. Another reason for a loss of offenders was a subsequent arrest or probation violation.

The risk score distributions of the offenders with one LSI, and those with multiple assessments, were compared with the LSI national norms score distributions for offenders in community corrections and prison (Andrews, & Bonta, 2003). (See Figure 1.) The national male and female norms were combined at an 80/20 ratio for male and female offenders to match the ratio of males and females in the current population of offenders. The total offender population's LSI distribution was similar to the score distributions of the national corrections norm sample, and the risk level of the sample of offenders with multiple LSI assessments was about midway between a normal corrections population and a normal prison population.

Figure 1

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

9

Comparison with National Corrections and Prison Risk Norms of Offender Population (N=4919) and the Sample of Offenders with Multiple Assessments (N=1833)

Design and Materials

Data Variables. The records used in this study were provided in a flat file format with one record for each LSI assessment. Each record had the names and birthdates of offenders, which were matched to two separate databases, a court services database that tracked probation violations that resulted in a prison commitment, and a BCA database containing arrest and conviction records. The initial LSI was done after arrest, and before conviction, which allowed the timing of arrests occurring before the LSI to be differentiated from those after the LSI. The BCA database also contained demographic data such as age, gender, and race. In total, 97% of the LSI-R records were matched to BCA records.

The independent variables used in this study were continuous (Age at first assessment, LSI-R score, Assessment Number, Days Between Assessments, and Score Change), and dichotomous (Male, White, Switched Raters). The dependent variable was a dichotomous

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

10

variable called Any Violation (AV) that was a composite of arrest leading to conviction and/or probation violation leading to a prison commitment.

Procedure

The initial LSI database was exported to an SQL database and manipulated with Microsoft Visual Basic. Additional fields were added to the LSI-R SQL table as needed and populated with arrest and conviction data provided by the BCA, probation violation data provided by court services, or computations from other fields. AV was calculated by determining whether any further arrests or probation violations occurred in the year after the first conviction. Arnold (2007) discussed the process in more detail. It should be noted that a slightly different procedure was used to calculate the AV variable in this study. Arnold used the completion date of the LSI to calculate AV, and this study used the creation date, since some offenders were arrested after the LSI creation date, but before the completion date. One of the more useful data manipulations done was to flatten the data still further by putting all of the LSI scores and change scores in each record, which then could be selected by Assessment Number. After the data was manipulated it was exported to SPSS. The calculations done in this study were done in SPSS or Excel. The OLS calculations were done in accordance with the methods proposed by Singer and Willett (2003) for analyzing individual growth curves.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Dynamic Predictive Validity of the LSI and the Temporal Stability of Risk

The correlation rates were calculated between LSI scores and violation by one year after each LSI for LSI 1,2,3, & 4 (Mean interval = approx. 7 mo., S.D.= 3 mo.). The results are shown in Figure 1 (all $p < .001$). Reading across the rows, it is clear that subsequent LSI scores have consistently higher predictive validity coefficients than LSI 1. This is similar to the previous results found by others. Reading down the columns, it is clear that the LSI scores do not degrade with time, as would be predicted if the risk levels were changing over time. The LSI scores not only don't get worse, they appear to improve over time in some cases. At the very least, they are equivalent. This indicates that the underlying propensity for rule violation must have a high degree of temporal stability or, if risk levels are unstable, they are unstable in a nonlinear fashion.

Figure 1.

Correlation Between LSI Score and Violation by One Year after each LSI Assessment

	LSI 1	LSI 2	LSI 3	LSI 4
Sample 1(N=3216)				
After LSI 1	.275			
Sample 2 (N=1182)				
After LSI 1	.196			
After LSI 2	.245	.338		
Sample 3 (N=614)				
After LSI 1	.220			
After LSI 2	.250	.323		
After LSI 3	.227	.313	.344	
Sample 4 (N=287)				
After LSI 1	.225			
After LSI 2	.241	.289		
After LSI 3	.209	.279	.274	
After LSI 4	.218	.338	.353	.347

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

12

Inter-Rater and Intra-Rater Effects on Score Changes between Assessments

In order to observe the effects of changing raters, and the score changes due to the learning curve, the LSI scores of offenders with four LSI assessments (N=510) were grouped by 5-point intervals of score change, centered on 0, and plotted in figure 2A. The changes in LSI scores are markedly different for LSI 1-2 than from LSI 2-3, and LSI 3-4. This process was repeated for offenders who switched raters from LSI 1-2 and kept the same rater from LSI 2-3 and LSI 3-4 (N=178), and the plots were placed in Figure 2B. Again, it is clear that LSI 1-2 shows a marked difference in scoring. When the same rater is kept on all three LSI assessments (N=144), as shown in Figure 2C, it is clear that all three distributions are much closer in shape. When Figures 2B and 2C are compared, the difference in scoring due to a switch in raters is observed. This, from a visual standpoint indicates that switching raters has an effect on scoring. Figure 2D shows the distributions when raters are switched on all three LSI assessments. A subsection of offenders who had the same rater from LSI 3-4 (N=58) show less change in score than any of the other sets of score changes between LSI assessments.

The intra-rater differences in the magnitude of scoring from LSI 1-2 compared with LSI 2-3, and LSI 3-4 can be seen in Figure 2C. There is no shift in central tendency, indicating that rating is consistent within the same raters, but the dispersion in the changes in scores is greater from LSI 1-2, compared with LSI 2-3, and LSI 3-4, supporting the learning curve hypothesis.

The consistency in the amount of change in approximately equal seven-month intervals (S.D. = 3 mo.) between LSI 2-3, and LSI 3-4, is remarkable. This indicates that the temporal instability of offender risk is constant over time. This would have important implications for practice, as the group level of change appears to be predictable, and could be used to set reassessment guidelines.

Figure 2.

Percentages of Offenders for each 5 Point Change in LSI Score for LSI 1-2, LSI 2-3, and LSI 3-4

A number of descriptive and analytical statistics were calculated for the groups of offenders shown in Figure 2, and placed in Table 2. The greater parts of these statistics are provided for reference. There are four sections, each with three columns and three sets of calculations. There are descriptive statistics for both the score changes, and the absolute values of the score changes. The absolute values of the score changes are provided because the almost perfect symmetry between increases and decreases in score changes renders the mean values of the score changes practically useless for determining the magnitude of change. A set of t tests was done between the columns to determine whether the means were the same.

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

14

In Column 2, note that when the rater is switched from LSI 1-2, both the mean score change, and mean absolute values of the score changes are significantly greater than when the rater is held constant. In the case of the raters held constant, there is no significant difference in scoring. Note that the correlation between LSI 1 and LSI 2, LSI 3, and LSI 4 is low when the rater is switched, but high between LSI 2, LSI 3, and LSI 4 when the rater is held constant. This suggests that some of the temporal instability of offender risk level for LSI 1-N is simply due to inter-rater instability.

In Column 3, note that when the rater is kept the same between assessments the mean level of change is not significantly different between LSI 1-2, LSI 2-3, or LSI 3-4. This indicates that the same rater rates offenders consistently. Note that the mean absolute level of score change is significantly different between LSI 1-2 and LSI 2-3, but not significantly different between LSI 2-3, and LSI 3-4. This supports the learning curve hypothesis that the rater is getting to know the offender better from LSI 1-2. There is no differential learning effect from LSI 2-3, or from LSI 3-4. The correlation rates indicate that the LSI 1 scores have a lower correlation rate with LSI 3, and LSI 4, suggesting that temporal instability of risk in this case may be due to an interaction effect between the rater and the offender, rather than an actual instability of offender risk.

In Column 4, when score changes are compared for rater switched LSI 1-2 and rater switched LSI 2-3, no significant differences are seen between the mean levels of real and absolute change. When this is contrasted with Column 2, the differences between switching raters and keeping raters the same are seen. The relative differences between the means and standard deviations support the contention that switching raters and the rater learning curve both add to score changes.

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

15

Table 2.

Score Change Statistics and Absolute Score Change Statistics and Inter-correlation Rates for Offenders with Four or More LSI Assessments

Sample LSI Test/Retest Switched	Column 1 All			Column 2 Switch 1-2, Same 2-4			Column 3 Same Rater 1-4			Column 4 Switch 1-2, 2-3, Split 3-4			
	1-2	2-3	3-4	1-2 Yes	2-3 No	3-4 No	1-2 No	2-3 No	3-4 No	1-2 Yes	2-3 Yes	3-4 Yes	3-4 No
N	510	510	510	178	178	178	144	144	144	92	92	34	58
Score Change between Assessments													
Mean	-56	-29	-.11	-2.43	-.63	-.08	-.01	-.40	-.75	.35	1.64	-1.56	-.34
S.D.	6.589	5.821	5.798	6.33	5.09	5.08	5.51	4.16	4.12	7.41	8.01	8.37	6.21
Median	0	0	0	-3	0	0	0	0	-0.5	0	0	-2	0
Mode	0	0	0	-5	0	1	0	0	0	-1	0	-2	1
Min.	-18	-19	-29	-18	-18	-25	-18	-14	-17	-14	-14	-15	-29
Max.	27	25	27	15	16	15	27	14	10	20	21	27	11
Range	45	44	56	33	34	40	45	28	27	34	35	42	40
t		-.708	.493		-2.962	1.021		.664	-.726		-.794		.794
Sig.		.479	.622		.003	.308		.507	.469		.428		.429
Absolute Value of Score Change Between Assessments													
Mean	5.09	3.99	4.12	5.42	3.58	3.60	3.88	2.73	2.80	5.80	5.97	6.26	4.21
S.D.	4.32	4.10	4.39	3.98	3.40	3.49	4.02	3.13	3.05	4.58	5.55	5.66	4.54
Median	4	3	3	5	3	3	3	2	2	5	4	4.5	3
Mode	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	0	1	3	1	2	1
Min.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Max.	27	25	29	18	18	25	27	14	17	20	21	27	29
t		4.187	.181		4.669	.031		2.713	.191		-.057		-1.912
Sig.		.000	.856		.000	.975		.007	.849		.954		.059
Correlations Between LSI Scores^a													
	LSI1	LSI2	LSI3	LSI1	LSI2	LSI3	LSI1	LSI2	LSI3	LSI1	LSI2	LSI3	LSI3
LSI2	.684			.703			.803			.504			
LSI3	.582	.763		.569	.814		.785	.881		.398	.395		
LSI4	.572	.709	.772	.572	.784	.816	.745	.829	.880	.355	.305**	.451**	.676

a: All p<.001 unless noted, ** = p<.01

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

16

Determining the Clinically Significant Level of Change

In order to determine the level of change needed to produce a clinically significant change, the Reliable Change Index (RCI) for the LSI was calculated using the correlation rate between the LSI 1 and LSI 2 scores for the 0-90 day interval, as this would most likely be a time period in which no real change occurred. Note that one of the requirements of the RCI is that the correlation between assessments needed to be calculated in a period of zero change. The formula for the RCI at a 95% confidence interval is $RCI = 1.96 * \text{SQRT}(2) * \text{SQRT}(1 - r_{1-2}) * S.D.\#1$. The correlation between assessments at 90 days was $r_{1-2} = .859$ (N=20). Using the standard deviation of 8.443 that was found for the LSI 1 score distribution, the RCI is 8.8. This indicates that the percentages of offenders who changed more than 8 points could be assumed to have a clinically significant change in LSI score.

Determining the Magnitude of the Effect of Score Changes on Predictive Accuracy

Since the clinically significant change concept has not been tested with the LSI, and it is not clear what score change is needed to create a significant difference in predictive accuracy, a logistic regression model was created using violation at one year as the dependent variable, and age, race and gender, as well as the LSI 2 risk level as controls. A set of dummy variables, coded a 0 or 1 to indicate the level of changes in scores, were created to determine the level of score change needed to achieve a significant level of improvement in predictive accuracy. Offenders with three LSI assessments and at least a one-year follow-up period after LSI 3 (N=615) were used for this test. The results in Table 6 indicate that a change of 9 or more points is required for the LSI to detect a change in the likelihood of recidivism. This test provides a direct confirmation of the accuracy of the RCI, as a cutoff score of 8 or less is non-significant.

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

17

The dummy score change levels used in Table 3 cover a range of scores because the small number of offenders at each level would not allow analysis with smaller categories. Another logistic regression test, not shown, was done to bracket the level of score change needed from LSI 1-2, and LSI 2-3 to significantly predict violation. It was found that a score change of 4 points between LSI 1-2 improved the accuracy of prediction after LSI 2. This smaller level of change required to improve predictive accuracy is consistent with the improved accuracy of LSI 2 scores over LSI 1 scores. The score change needed from LSI 2-3 to significantly increase the predictive accuracy of LSI 2 in the 1-year period after LSI 3 was 9 points.

These three tests each independently confirm that a score change of 9 points or more is needed before a change in LSI score reflects a measurable change in risk. The generalizability of this result is not clear, but this does provide some initial guidance for corrections officials.

Table 3.

Logistic Regression Model for Comparison of Score Change to Predict Violation in One-Year Compared with Reference Interval of No Score Change (N=615)

	N	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95.0% C.I. for EXP(B)	
								Lower	Upper
Age		-.010	.011	.974	1	.324	.990	.969	1.010
White		-.422	.249	2.880	1	.090	.656	.403	1.068
Male		.241	.284	.719	1	.396	1.272	.729	2.218
LSI 2 Score		.118	.016	56.879	1	.000	1.125	1.091	1.160
Score Change LSI 2 to Final									
Changed 9 or more down	59	-1.561	.544	8.243	1	.004	.210	.072	.609
Changed 5 to 8 down	88	-.715	.472	2.298	1	.130	.489	.194	1.233
Changed 1 to 4 down	186	-.678	.431	2.480	1	.115	.508	.218	1.180
Reference – No Change	59								
Changed 1 to 4 up	127	.073	.436	.028	1	.868	1.075	.458	2.526
Changed 5 to 8 up	52	.656	.485	1.827	1	.176	1.927	.744	4.990
Changed 9 or more up	44	1.605	.496	10.493	1	.001	4.980	1.885	13.156
Constant		-3.490	.791	19.445	1	.000	.031		

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

18

Measuring Between Group Changes in Risk Level to Determine Optimal Reassessment Period

In order to provide corrections officials an indication of the level of change in risk level to expect over time, the offenders with 3 or more assessments and the same rater (N=615) were split by amount of time between LSI 2 and the final LSI. The first five groups included offenders split by 6 month intervals through 30 months, and the sixth group included all offenders with more than 30 months between LSI 2 and the final LSI. ANOVA analysis of ages and Chi-Square analysis of race and gender revealed that the demographic characteristics of these sub-samples of offenders were all similar. The seventh column is included for comparison and consists of all offenders whose rater changed from LSI 2 to the Final LSI.

The results, shown in Table 4, indicate that there is a fairly high degree of temporal stability, as indicated by the correlation rates between the two sets of LSI scores, until after 30 months. A separate calculation using a linear regression model (not shown) indicated that the mean score changes for offenders in the 19-24, and 25-30 month test-retest periods were significantly different from the mean score change of offenders who had shorter (0-6 month) test-retest intervals, but the mean score change for offenders in the 31-56 month group were not significantly different from the mean score change of the offenders in the 0-6 month group. The only time period with a significant absolute difference in the level of change was the 31-56 month time period. Aside from a slight jump in the temporal stability of risk for the offenders with 25-30 months between assessments, it appears that the amount of accumulated change in risk increases in a linear fashion over time. One item of interest is the fact that there would appear to never be a time when there was no change in risk level. In the 0-6 month period, almost 10% of offenders had a clinically significant change, and less than 50% could be considered to not have changed at all because of a change in score of only -2 to 2 points.

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

19

In terms of temporal instability, it appears that changes in risk level are the rule, but the accumulation of changes in risk level over time is slow. Interpretation is guarded as this is a between group comparison, and the groups could vary in unseen ways.

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

20

Table 4.

Statistics for Second and Final LSI Scores, and Score Changes between Second and Final LSI, Grouped by Time between Assessments for Offenders with Same Rater at Both Assessments. Statistics for Offenders with a Switch in Raters between Assessments are Included.

	Months Between Assessments						Total Same Rater	Switched Raters
	0-6 Mo.	7-12 Mo.	13-18 Mo.	19-24 Mo.	25-30 Mo.	31-56 Mo.		
N	115	222	163	52	31	32	615	347
LSI 2								
Mean	22.7	23.3	23.6	23.3	26.5	23.7	23.4	26.4
S.D.	7.3	8.4	9.2	7.6	9.2	8.2	8.4	7.9
Final LSI								
Mean	20.8	22.0	22.5	23.3	26.4	22.4	22.3	26.5
S.D.	7.9	8.9	9.3	8.0	9.5	8.6	8.8	8.2
Score Change LSI 2-Final								
Mean	-1.91	-1.32	-1.10	-.06	-.13	-1.34	-1.21	.06
S.D.	4.74	4.61	5.43	5.91	5.85	6.51	5.15	8.36
Minimum	-18	-17	-17	-16	-16	-15	-18	-24
Maximum	15	13	13	10	10	11	15	27
Absolute Score Change LSI 2-Final								
Mean	3.69	3.46	4.04	4.56	4.45	5.47	3.90	6.45
S.D.	3.53	3.31	3.78	3.70	3.70	3.65	3.57	5.31
Range	18	17	21	16	16	14	21	27
r (p<.001)	.758	.765	.814	.661	.788	.491	.755	.541
Percentages of Offenders in Each 5-Point Score Change Interval								
-27 thru -23								.3
-22 thru -18	.9		.6				.3	.9
-17 thru -13	.9	1.4	2.5	3.8	3.2	3.1	2.0	3.5
-12 thru -8	10.4	9.0	9.2	3.8	9.7	15.6	9.3	11.8
-7 thru -3	27.0	23.4	23.3	26.9	19.4	28.1	24.4	22.2
-2 thru 2	48.7	51.4	42.3	34.6	35.5	25.0	44.9	26.8
3 thru 7	9.6	12.2	17.8	17.3	29.0	18.8	14.8	16.1
8 thru 12	1.7	1.8	3.7	13.5	3.2	9.4	3.7	10.7
13 thru 17	.9	.9	.6				.7	3.5
18 thru 22								3.5
23 thru 27								.9
% Clinically Sig. (>= 9)	9.6	8.6	14.1	15.4	12.9	25.0	11.9	29.4

CONCLUSIONS

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

21

Several tentative conclusions can be drawn from the preceding analyses, with any permanent conclusions being held in reserve until the results of these analyses are replicated. The tentative conclusions can be broken down into general conclusions, which have to do with measurement issues in a test-retest environment, and sample specific conclusions, which are limited to the non-random groups of offenders that were used in these analyses.

The general conclusions are that there is a learning curve for raters who use interview based assessment instruments, and that the first assessment is generally less accurate than subsequent assessments. There is a larger score change when raters are switched between assessments, and score changes will be difficult to interpret when the same rater is not used on both assessments. A general conclusion could also be drawn that there is some non-zero level of score change that cannot be assumed to be significant enough to make a difference in the outcome of interest, in this case, violation rate. The cutoff level, called a Reliable Change Index (RCI), can be determined on a sample-by-sample basis until a general cutoff score is found.

The sample specific conclusions are that offender risk levels are stable enough so that the LSI is not a better predictor of risk in the 21-33 month period than in the 0-12 month period. Changes in LSI score need to be 9-points or greater after LSI 2, when the same rater is used, in order for the change in LSI score to indicate a significant change in arrest rate. Only about 9.0% of offenders have a 9-point or greater change in score in a one-year period. This change is generally preceded and followed by a smaller change in score in the opposite direction, resulting in a less than 9-point change across three assessments. Of the approximately 9.0% of offenders who do have a 9-point change in score, none of the offenders who have a 9-point increase maintain the 9-point increase in score until the next assessment, and only 1/2 of the offenders with a 9-point decrease, or 1/4 of the 9% of offenders with a 9-point change maintain that change

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

22

over the next seven months. This zig-zag pattern results in a net total of about 15% of offenders with a 9-point change in the 1-2 year time period and about 20% with a net change in the 2-3 year time period. At no time is there ever a period of no significant change.

When linear trends are plotted over periods of 2-4 years, 18.0% of offenders have a significant linear decrease in LSI scores over time, and 8.4% have a significant linear increase in scores. The rest of the offenders, totaling 73.6% had no significant linear change in score. A visual inspection indicated that the offender risk levels seemed to fluctuate in a nonlinear cyclic fashion over time. A plot of the total range of score changes indicated that there was a peak at the 3-point score change level, followed by an almost equal number of offenders (10% each) at the 4-10 point change levels, and a few offenders with very large levels of change. When the natural log of the offender distribution at each level of score change was plotted, it appeared to follow a power law distribution.

The rank order of the offender risk levels is maintained at a fairly high level of approximately $r = .70-.80$ until the 31-56 month time period, when it drops to $r=.50$. The percentage of offenders with a 9-point change in score jumps to 25% in this time period. These two measurements indicate that rank order changes in score do occur over longer periods of time. This result tends to be contrary to Gottfredson and Hirschi's (1990) stability of self-control thesis, and supportive, in principle, of Sampson and Laub's (1993) thesis that events can change the level of criminal propensity. There is not enough information to indicate the cause the rank order changes in risk level at this point.

Following a more in-depth review of each of the analyses done, the general implications from these results will be broken down into practice, research, and theoretical domains, and discussed in-depth.

The Dynamic Predictive Validity of the LSI and Temporal Stability of Risk

The test to determine whether offender risk levels are temporally unstable shows that the previous LSI scores did not become less accurate over time as would be suggested by a linear inertial model of change. This suggests that risk levels were either stable in the 21 months from LSI 1 to LSI 4, or the changes in risk were nonlinear in nature. The dynamic predictive accuracy of the LSI improved substantially from LSI 1 to LSI 2, indicating that a reassessment at 6 months might be a good idea if a more accurate risk score was desired. This analysis provided insufficient evidence, by itself, to indicate what a good reassessment period would be, but the results indicate that 7-21 months was too short of a time period, since the LSI 1 scores predicted recidivism equally as well over the 0-12 month period as the 21-33 month period.

Effects of Changing Raters and Learning Curve on Score Changes between Assessments

Both changing raters between assessments, and the effects of the learning curve from LSI 1 to LSI 2 have an effect on the level of score change between assessments. There is an approximately 2 point higher mean change in both score and absolute score when changing raters vs. keeping the same rater. This tends to skew results when trying to interpret changes in scores. There is about a 1-point higher absolute mean change in score from LSI 1-2 than from LSI 2-3, or LSI 3-4, when the rater is kept the same between assessments. Given the significant increase in predictive validity that occurs from LSI 1-2, it is probably be safe to assume that the increase in score change is due to a learning curve effect.

For day to day applications of practice, the change in score may not be enough to be concerned with, given the 9-point score change required to indicate a change in risk level, but for

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

24

research applications dealing with changes in risk level over time, it appears that the lower accuracy for the first LSI would make it a poor candidate to draw conclusions from. These two results suggest that additional research is needed to determine whether studies examining changes in behavior should keep the same rater between assessments and throw out the first assessment due to problems with reduced accuracy.

It should be noted that many of the subsequent analyses done in this study would have been impossible if different raters were used or LSI 1 scores were included. Attempts had been made for 18 months to analyze changes in risk level using scores with different raters on each assessment and including the LSI 1 scores, and analyses kept producing inconsistent results. It was only when the rater was held constant and the LSI 1 scores were dropped that the true nature of change could be assessed.

The Precision of Offender Risk Assessment Instruments

To significantly increase predictive accuracy, a score change of 9-points or greater was needed. This result only pertained to the periods after the initial learning curve from LSI 1-2. The change in the LSI score needed to significantly predict a change in recidivism rates from LSI 1-2 was only 4 points. This could be due to the higher accuracy of the LSI 2 scores over the LSI 1 scores. Using classic test theory, any score can be thought of as the sum of a true score and some amount of error (Nunnally, & Bernstein, 1994; p. 224). A change in score from LSI 1 to LSI 2 is probably partly due to a reduction in the error coefficient, and it therefore takes less of a change in score to make a difference in the accuracy level.

The implications of the clinically significant change results for practice could be significant. Knowing the level of change required to predict a change in risk could provide

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

25

guidance for corrections officials trying to interpret score changes. Small changes in score can be assumed to not predict a significant likelihood that risk has changed. These results could provide a more rational method for determining reassessment periods. It probably does not make sense to reassess someone who does not appear to be making significant changes in their lives. Some caution is needed before acting on these results however; as these results must be replicated before any policy changes are made.

Limitations of the Present Study

The data used in the analyses for this study was selected in several non-random ways and so generalization to other populations of offenders would be problematic. There were several steps to the non-random selection process. The corrections officials had censored the data initially by eliminating low risk offenders. Reductions made to get quality samples, such as eliminating test-retest pairs where the same rater was not used on each assessment and eliminating the first set of scores, censored the data even further in many nonrandom ways. No policy decisions should be made from this the results of this study. The sole purpose of this study is to guide future research efforts. Because the data collection interval was set at seven months, there could be much more fluctuation in risk levels than is indicated by these results. The patterns appear to show a gradual pattern to changes in risk, but it could be that scores change even more rapidly, and also with greater magnitude of the fluctuations, than these “point in time” assessments indicate. Further analysis would need to be done with random samples over shorter time periods to determine what the actual rate of fluctuation is.

Suggestions for Future Research

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

26

Further replication efforts of this group level study are needed with larger samples to determine whether the levels of changes in risk vary over time in the same way for each population of offenders. Replication efforts are also needed using shorter time periods to determine the frequency of fluctuations.

An analysis of individual items should be done using longitudinal panel research methods developed by sociologists for studying survey data. The data used in this study is much too sparse for such methods, and so more data would need to be collected. Exploratory studies could be conducted by culling records from much larger data sets using the rules provided by these analyses, which are to only use data from reassessments that keep the same rater, and throw out the first assessment. There are potentially millions of records in the U.S. alone, so datasets of several thousand offenders in community corrections settings could be acquired. The cost of these datasets would be negligible, since interviews are already conducted.

Going forward, datasets should be built with complete longitudinal sets of data for all offenders or, at the very least, for random samples of offenders. There may be related datasets already in place that provide longitudinal data on populations of offenders. Bridges (2005) indicates the Home Office in England had set a goal of assessing offenders every 16 weeks with the Offender Assessment System (OASys), a risk scoring system similar to the LSI. If that has progressed, the data needed is simply awaiting a way to analyze it.

References

- Andrews, Don A. 1982. "The Level of Supervisory Inventory (LSI): The First Follow-up."
Toronto: Ontario Ministry of Correctional Services.
- Andrews, Don A., and James Bonta. 1995. *LSI-R: The Level of Service Inventory-Revised User's Manual*. Toronto: Multi-Health Systems, Inc.
- Andrews, Don A., and James Bonta. 2003. *The LSI-R: Level of Service Inventory-Revised: U.S. Norms Manual Supplement*. Toronto: Multi-Health Systems, Inc.
- Andrews, Don A. and James Bonta. 2006. *The Psychology of Criminal Conduct*, 4th ed. Newark, NJ: LexisNexis.
- Andrews, Don A., James Bonta, and J. Stephen Wormith. 2006. "The recent past and near future of risk and/or need assessment." *Crime & Delinquency*, 52(1):7-27.
- Andrews Don A., and Craig Dowden. 2006. "Risk Principle of Case Classification in Correctional Treatment: A Meta-analytic Investigation." *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology* 50(1):88-100.
- Andrews, Don A., and David Robinson. 1984. "The Level of Supervision Inventory: Second Report." Toronto: Ontario Ministry of Correctional Services.
- Arnold, Thomas K. 2007. "Dynamic changes in the Level of Service Inventory-Revised (LSI-R) and the effects on prediction accuracy." Unpublished Master's Thesis, St. Cloud State University, St. Cloud, Minnesota.
- Ashby, W. Ross. 1956. *An Introduction to Cybernetics*. London: Methuen & Co LTD.
- Baird, S., Heinz, R., & B. Bemus. 1979. *Wisconsin case classification/staff deployment project: A two-year follow-up report*. Madison, WI: Department of Health and Social Services. Bureau of Community Corrections.

Bak, Per. 1997. *How Nature Works: the science of self-organized criticality*. New York: Copernicus.

Bateson, Gregory. 1979. *Mind and Nature: A Necessary Unity*. New York: E. P. Dutton.

Bird, Richard J. 2003. *Chaos and Life: Complexity and Order in Evolution and Thought*. New York: Columbia University Press.

Blalock, Hubert M. Jr. (1979). *Social Statistics*, 2nd Ed. Tokyo: McGraw-Hill Kogakusha, Ltd.

Bonta, James. 2002. "Offender Risk Assessment: Guidelines For Selection and Use." *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 29(4):355-379.

Blumstein, Alfred, Jacqueline Cohen, Jeffrey Roth, and Christy A. Visher. 1986. *Criminal Careers and Career Criminals*, Vol. 1. Washington, DC: National Academy Press.

Bridges, Andrew. 2005. "Realising the Potential. A short focused inspection on the Offender Assessment System (OASys)." London: HM Inspectorate of Probation.

Brown, Shelly L. 2002. "The dynamic prediction of criminal recidivism." Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Queen's University, Kingston, Ontario, Canada.

Burgess, E. W. 1928. "Factors determining success or failure on parole." In A. A. Bruce, E. W. Burgess, J. Landesco, & A.J. Harno (Eds.) *The workings of the indeterminate sentence law and the parole system in Illinois*. Springfield, IL: Illinois Committee on Indeterminate-Sentence Law and Parole.

Burnett, Ros. 2004. "To Reoffend or Not to Reoffend? The Ambivalence of Convicted Property Offenders", in S. Maruna and R. Immarigeon (eds) *After Crime and Punishment: Pathways to Offender Reintegration*, pp. 152–80. Cullompton, Devon: Willan.

- Burt, Callie Harbin, Ronald L. Simons, and Leslie G. Simons. 2006. "A longitudinal test of the effects of parenting and the stability of self-control: Negative evidence for the general theory of crime." *Criminology*, 44:353-96.
- Bushway, Shawn D., Alex R. Piquero, Lisa M. Briody, Elizabeth Cauffman, and Paul Mazerolle. 2001. "An empirical framework for studying desistance as a process." *Criminology*, 39(2):491-513.
- Campbell, Donald T., and David A. Kenny. 1999. *A Primer on Regression Artifacts*. New York: Guilford Press.
- Crocker, Linda, & Algina, James. 1986. *Introduction to Classical & Modern Test Theory*. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Group/Thompson Learning.
- Cronbach, Lee J., Lita Furby. 1970. "How should we measure "change" - or should we?" *Psychological Bulletin*, 74(1):68-80.
- Clauset, Aaron, Cosma Rohilla Shalizi, and M.E.J. Newman. 2007. "Power-law distributions in empirical data." Donloaded on November 11, 2008 from <http://arxiv.org/abs/0706.1062>.
- Cook, Thomas D., and Donald T. Campbell. 1979. *Quasi-experimentation: Design and Analysis Issues for Field Settings*. Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin.
- Douglas, Kevin S., and Jennifer L. Skeem. 2005. "Violence risk assessment: Getting specific about being dynamic." *Psychology, Public Policy, and Law*, 11(3):347-383.
- Elder, Glen H., Jr. (1985). "Perspectives on the Life Course." pp. 23-49 In Elder, Glen H., Jr., ed. *Life course dynamics: Trajectories and transitions, 1968-1980*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.

- Ezell, Michael E., and Lawrence E. Cohen. 2005. *Desisting from Crime: Continuity and Change in Long-Term Crime Patterns of Serious Chronic Offenders*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Farrington, David P., Bernard Gallagher, Lynda Morley, Raymond J. St. Ledger, and Donald J. West. 1986. "Unemployment, School Leaving, and Crime." *British Journal of Criminology*, 26:335-356.
- Feigenbaum, Mitchell. 1983. "Universal behavior in nonlinear systems." *Physica*, 7D(1-3):16-39.
- Flores, Anthony W., Christopher T. Lowenkamp, Alexander M. Holsinger, and Edward J. Latessa. 2006. "Predicting outcome with the Level of Service Inventory-Revised: The importance of implementation integrity." *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 34:523-529.
- Gemmill, Gary, and Smith, Charles. 1985. "A Dissipative Structure Model of Organization Transformation." *Human Relations*, 38:751-756.
- Gendreau, Paul, Claire Goggin, and Paula Smith. 2002. "Is the PCL-R Really the "Unparalleled" Measure of Offender Risk? A Lesson in Knowledge Cumulation." *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 29(4):397-426.
- Gendreau, Paul, Tracy Little, and Claire Goggin. 1996. "A Meta-analysis of the Predictors of Adult Offender Recidivism: What Works!" *Criminology*, 34(4):575-607.
- Glaser, Daniel. 1964. *The Effectiveness of a Prison and Parole System*. Indianapolis: Bobbs-Merrill.
- Glaze, Lauren E., and Thomas P. Bonczar. 2007. "Probation and Parole in the United States, 2006, Publication No. NCJ 220218." Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Justice, Bureau of Justice Statistics.

- Gottfredson, Michael R., and Travis Hirschi. 1990. *A General Theory of Crime*. Palo Alto, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Hart, Hornell. 1923. "Predicting parole success." *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, 14(3), 405-414.
- Harvey, David L. and Michael H. Reed. 1994. "The evolution of dissipative social systems." *Journal of Social and Evolutionary Systems*, 17:371-411.
- Hay, Carter, and Walter Forrest. 2006. "The Development of Self-Control: Examining Self-Control Theory's Stability Thesis." *Criminology*, 44(4):739-774.
- Hirschi, Travis, and Michael R. Gottfredson. 1983. "Age and the Explanation of Crime." *The American Journal of Sociology*, 89(3):552-584.
- Hirschi, Travis, and Michael R. Gottfredson. 2001. "Self-control theory." In *Explaining Criminals and Crime*, Raymond Paternoster and Ronet Bachman, eds. Los Angeles, CA: Roxbury.
- Horney, Julie, D., Wayne Osgood, and Ineke Haen Marshall. 1995. "Criminal Careers in the Short-Term: Intra-Individual Variability in Crime and its Relation to Local Life Circumstances." *American Sociological Review*, 60(5):655-673.
- Hubbard, Dana Jones, Lawrence F. Travis, III, and Edward J. Latessa. 2001. "Case Classification in Community Corrections: A National Survey of the State of the Art. Final report of grant no. 98-IJ-CX-0008 awarded by the National Institute of Justice." Cincinnati: University of Cincinnati Center for Criminal Justice Research.
- Jacobson, Neil S., William C. Follette, and Dirk Revenstorff. 1984. "Psychotherapy Outcome Research: Methods for Reporting Variability and Evaluating Clinical Significance." *Behavior Therapy*, 15: 336- 352.

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

32

- Jacobson, Neil S., and Paula Truax. 1991. "Clinical Significance: A Statistical Approach to Defining Meaningful Change in Psychotherapy Research." *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 59: 12–19.
- Janis, Irving L. 1959. "Decisional Conflicts: A Theoretical Analysis." *The Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 3(1):6-27.
- Janis, Irving L. and Leon Mann. 1977. *Decision Making*. New York: Free Press.
- Kazdin, Alan E., Helena Chmura Kraemer, Ronald C. Kessler, David J. Kupfer, and David R. Offord. 1997. "Contributions of Risk-factor Research to Developmental Psychopathology." *Clinical Psychology Review*, 17(4):375-406.
- Kelly, Janice R., and Joseph E. McGrath. 1988. *On Time and Method: Applied Social Research Methods Series*, Vol. 13. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications.
- Kreamer, Sally. 2004. "Quality Assurance and Training in Offender Assessment." *Assessment Issues for Managers. Topics in Community Corrections, Annual Issue 2004*. pp. 13-19. Washington DC: U.S. Department of Justice.
- Kroner, Daryl G., Jeremy F. Mills, and John R. Reddon. 2005. "A coffee can, factor analysis, and prediction of anti-social behavior: The structure of criminal risk." *International Journal of Law and Psychiatry*, 28: 360-374.
- Langan, Patrick A. and David J. Levin. 2002. "Recidivism of Prisoners Released in 1994". Bureau of Justice Statistics, Special Report (NCJ, 193427). Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Justice, Office of Justice Programs, National Institute of Justice.
- Lewin, Kurt. 1935. "Chapter 4: The Psychological Situations of Reward and Punishment." *A Dynamic Theory of Personality: Selected Papers*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

33

Lewin, Kurt. 1964. "Group dynamics and social change." In Amitai Etzioni & Eva Etzioni, E. Eds., *Social change*. New York: Basic Books, Inc.

Loeber, Rolf, and Marc Le Blanc. 1990. "Toward a developmental criminology." In Michael Tonry and Norval Morris, Eds. *Crime and Justice: A Review of Research*, Vol. 12:375-473. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press.

Martinson, Robert. 1974. "What Works? -- Questions and Answers About Prison Reform." *The Public Interest*, 10:22-54.

Maruna, Shadd. 2001. *Making Good: How Ex-Convicts Reform and Rebuild Their Lives*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association Books.

Matza, David. 1964. *Delinquency and drift*. New York: Wiley.

Minnesota Department of Corrections. 2006. "Classification and Assessment." Division Directive: 203.016, Issue Date: 3/7/06. Downloaded on August 25th, 2007 from <http://www.doc.state.mn.us/DocPolicy2/Document/203.016.htm>.

Mitchell, Ojmarrh, and Doris Layton MacKenzie. 2006. "The Stability and Resiliency of Self-Control in a Sample of Incarcerated Offenders." *Crime & Delinquency*, 52(3):432-449.

Molenaar, P.C.M. (2008). On the implications of the classical ergodic theorems: Analysis of developmental processes has to focus on intra-individual variation. *Developmental Psychobiology*, 50, 60-69.

Motiuk, Lawrence.L. 1991. "Antecedents and Consequences of Prison Adjustment: A Systematic Assessment and Reassessment Approach." Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario.

Motiuk, L. L., Bonta, J., & Andrews, D. A. (1990). Dynamic Predictive Criterion Validity in Offender Assessment. A paper presented at the Canadian Psychological Association Annual Convention, Ottawa, June, 1990.

Myers, Peter L, and Norman R. Salt. 2007. *Becoming An Addictions Counselor; A Comprehensive Text*. 2nd ed. Sudbury, MA: Jones and Bartlett Publishers.

Nagin, Daniel, and Raymond Paternoster. 2000. "Population Heterogeneity and State Dependence: State of the Evidence and Directions for Future Research." *Journal of Quantitative Criminology*, (16)2:117-144.

Nunnally, Jum C., and Ira H. Bernstein. 1994. *Psychometric Theory*, 3rd ed. New York: McGraw Hill.

Peters, Roger H., and Harry K. Wexler. "2005. Substance Abuse Treatment For Adults in the Criminal Justice System: A Treatment Improvement Protocol TIP 44. DHHS Publication No. (SMA) 05-4056." Rockville, MD: Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration.

Piquero, Alex R., John M. McDonald, and Karen F. Parker. 2002. "Race, Local Life Circumstances, and Criminal Activity." *Social Science Quarterly*, 83(3): 654–70.

Piquero, Alex R. 2004. "Somewhere Between Persistence and Desistence: The Intermittency of Criminal Careers." In S. Maruna & R. Immarigeon, Eds., *After crime and punishment: Pathways to offender reintegration*, pp. 102-125. Cullompton, Devon, UK: Willan.

Prochaska, James O., and Carlo C. DiClemente. 1983. "Stages and processes of self-change of smoking: Toward an integrative model of change." *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 51(3): 390-395.

- Prochaska, J. O., Carlo C. DiClemente, and Norcross, J. C. (1992). In search of how people change: Applications to addictive behavior. *American Psychologist*, 47, 1102-1114.
- Prochaska, James O., Wayne F. Velicer, Joseph S. Rossi, Michael G. Goldstein, Bess H. Marcus, William Rakowski, Christine Fiore, Lisa L. Harlow, Colleen A. Redding, Dena Rosenbloom, and Susan R. Rossi. 1994. "Stages of change and decisional balance for 12 problem behaviors." *Health Psychology*, 13(1):39-46.
- Raffaelli, Marcela, Lisa J. Crockett, and Yuh-Ling Shen. 2005. "Developmental stability and change in self-regulation from childhood to adolescence." *The Journal of Genetic Psychology*, 166:54-75.
- Raynor, Peter. 2007. "Risk and Need Assessment in British Probation: The Contribution of the LSI-R." *Psychology, Crime, & Law*, 13(2):125-138.
- Raynor, Peter, Jocelyn Kynch, Colin Roberts, and Simon Merrington. 2000. "Risk and Need Assessment in Probation Services: an Evaluation. Research Study 211." London: Home Office.
- Robins, Lee N. 1978. "Sturdy childhood predictors of adult antisocial behaviour: replications from longitudinal studies." *Psychological Medicine*, 8:611-622.
- Rogosa, David, David Brandt, & Michele Zimowski. 1982. "A growth curve approach to measurement of change." *Psychological Bulletin*, 92(3):726-748.
- Sampson, Robert J. and John H. Laub (1993). *Crime in the Making: Pathways and Turning Points Through Life*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Sampson, Robert J., & John H. Laub. 2003. "Life Course Desisters? Trajectories of Crime Among Delinquent Boys Followed to Age 70." *Criminology*, 41(3):555-592.

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

36

- Simon, Herbert A. 1955. "On a Class of Skew Distribution Functions". *Biometrika*, 42(3/4):425–440.
- Singer, Judith D., and John B. Willett. 2003. *Applied Longitudinal Data Analysis: Modeling Change and Event Occurrence*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Smith, Peter, & Dorcas Beaton. 2008. "Measuring Change in Psychosocial Working Conditions: Methodological Issues to Consider When Data are Collected at Baseline and One Follow-up Time Point." *Occupational Environmental Medicine*, 65: 288-296.
- Sutherland, Edwin H. 1947. *Principles of Criminology*. 4th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Turner, Michael G., and Alex R. Piquero. 2002. "The stability of self-control." *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 30:457–471.
- Velicer, Wayne F., Carlo C. DiClemente, James O. Prochaska, and Nancy Brandenberg. 1985. "A decisional balance measure for assessing and predicting smoking status." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 48(5):1279-1289.
- Vose, Brenda (2008). Assessing the Predictive Validity of the Level of Service Inventory-Revised: Recidivism Among Iowa Parolees and Probationers. (Doctoral Dissertation, University of Cincinnati) Retrieved from <http://etd.ohiolink.edu/send-pdf.cgi/VOSE%20BRENDA.pdf?ucin1212026987>.
- Warner, Sam B. 1923. "Factors Determining Parole from the Massachusetts Reformatory: The Report of the Director of Committee on Criminal Records and Statistics." *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, 14(2):172-207.

CAN CHANGES IN OFFENDER RISK BE MEASURED?

37

Willett, John B. (1989). "Some Results On Reliability For The Longitudinal Measurement Of Change: Implications For The Design Of Studies Of Individual Growth." *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 49:587-602.

Winfrey, L. Thomas Jr., Terrance J. Taylor, Ni He, and Finn-Aage Esbensen. 2006. "Self-Control and Variability Over Time: Multivariate Results Using a 5-Year, Multisite Panel of Youths." *Crime & Delinquency*, 52(2):253-286.

Zamble, Edward, and Vernon L. Quinsey. 1997. *The Criminal Recidivism Process*. New York: Cambridge University Press.